

EFFECT OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT ON AGING PROPERTIES OF GLASS FIBER/POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

This study discussed effect of molecular weight of matrix PP and maleic acid grafted PP (M-PP) on bending property and hydrothermal aging of GF/PP. High and low molecular weight matrix PP and M-PP were adopted. Modulus was more affected by molecular weight of matrix PP, while strength was more affected by molecular weight of M-PP.

Keywords: Polypropylene, Maleic acid grafted polypropylene, molecular weight

INTRODUCTION

Recently glass fibre/polypropylene (GF/PP) composite has been widely applied in automotive and electrical industries. Good mechanical properties of GF/PP are achieved by effective load transfer from matrix to reinforcing fibre, and therefore adhesion between glass fibre and PP is very important. However, the lack of functional groups in the chemical structure of PP prevents direct interaction with silane coupling agents that are usually treated onto glass fibres, thus limiting the interfacial adhesion unless chemical modification is performed on the resin. In order to achieve the good adhesion between glass fibre and PP maleic acid grafted PP (M-PP) is usually applied as modifier of interfacial adhesion [1-17] and it is compounded with matrix PP during compounding and pelletizing process. M-PP is compatible with PP and it is also reactive with silane coupling agent as glass fibre surface treatment. The mechanical properties of GF/PP are affected by the molecular weight of PP. However, the effects of molecular weight of matrix PP and M-PP and their interaction on mechanical properties of GF/PP have not been clear. As increasing the application of GF/PP the material recycling has been demanded to achieve the environmental friendliness. During the recycling process the material was subjected to the thermal history, and it brings the reduction of molecular weight of PP. The reduction of molecular weight of PP may bring the undesirable effects to the mechanical properties of recycled GF/PP.

Therefore it is important to understand the effect of molecular weight on the physical properties of GF/PP.

From this background this study discussed the effect of molecular weights of matrix PP and M-PP on bending properties of GF/PP injection mouldings. In addition, the specimens were aged hydrothermally in order to attack the interphase, and the changes of bending properties were measured. In order to discuss the effect of molecular weight on fracture behaviour the acoustic emission (AE) was monitored during the bending tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2 types of PP with different molecular weight ($M_w=19,000$ [noted as L] and $310,000$ [noted as H]) were prepared as matrix and 2 types of M-PP with different molecular weight ($M_w=21,000$ [noted as 1] and $142,000$ [noted as 2]) were prepared as interphase modifier. These materials and glass fibre were compounded and pelletized. The fibre weight fraction was 20wt% and the addition of M-PP was 1wt%. Compounding was conducted at 240°C and 300rpm by twin screw extruder. 4 types of specimen (L1, L2, H1 and H2) were prepared by injection moulding at moulding temperature of 230°C . The geometry of specimen was 127mm in length, 12mm in width and 3mm in thickness.

In order to discuss the effect of molecular weight on the mechanical properties the bending test was performed with simultaneous monitoring of acoustic emission (AE). 3-point bending test was performed for the virgin specimens and the specimens soon after aging (wet) and parched after aging (dry) in order to discuss the effects of water retention in the specimens. Bending test was performed by a universal testing machine (AG-50KNI, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan) at a constant crosshead speed of 1mm/min with 48mm span in air at room temperature. During bending test, acoustic emission (AE) from the specimen was monitored in order to evaluate the fracture behaviour. AE signal was monitored by 7600 series AE instrument (NF Corporation, Japan). Two types of AE transducers with different resonant frequencies of 140kHz and 1MHz were attached onto the specimen, and AE signals were monitored with the gain of 40dB and the threshold of 100mV. Here, the transducer with 140kHz resonant frequency mainly detects matrix dominant fracture, while the transducer with 1MHz resonant frequency mainly detects fibre dominant fracture [18].

In order to discuss the interfacial adhesion, some specimens were aged in distilled water at 80°C . Under the aging condition the interphase was attacked by diffused/penetrated water and the interfacial adhesion could be discussed by measuring the bending properties. After pre-determined periods of immersion, bending properties and fracture behaviour were also evaluated by 3-point bending and AE monitoring. Aging periods were 10, 300 and 1000 hours.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bending Properties and AE Characteristics of Virgin Specimens

Figure 1 shows the bending stress-deflection curves for the virgin (un-aged) specimens. The initial slopes in the stress-deflection curves were almost the same in the specimens

Figure 1 Comparison of bending stress-deflection curves for virgin specimens.

Figure 2 Comparison of bending moduli for virgin specimens.

Figure 3 Comparison of bending strengths for virgin specimens.

with the same matrix PP. On the other hand, the fracture deflections were almost the same in the specimens with the same M-PP. From this result it is considered that the matrix affected the deformation under low stress, while the M-PP as interphase modifier affected the deformation capability.

Figure 2 shows the effect of molecular weight on bending modulus for virgin specimens. The lower molecular weight of matrix PP and the higher molecular weight of M-PP

Figure 4 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for virgin L1 specimen.

Figure 5 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for virgin L2 specimen.

brought the higher bending modulus. By using lower molecular weight of matrix PP brought 8% higher modulus than the higher molecular weight of matrix PP, while the effect of molecular weight of M-PP on modulus was quite poor than matrix PP.

Figure 3 shows the effect of molecular weight on bending strength for virgin specimens. As same as the modulus, the lower molecular weight of matrix PP and the higher molecular weight of M-PP brought the higher bending strength. However, the effect of M-PP on strength was much higher than matrix PP, and this trend was opposite in case of modulus. In particular, high molecular weight of M-PP significantly improved the strength compared with low molecular weight, and the strengths of L2 and H2 were 25% higher than those of L1 and H1. It is considered that strong molecular entanglement occurred in the specimen with high molecular weight of M-PP because of its long molecular chain. In addition, many grafted maleic acid as reactive point in molecular chain existed in long molecular chain and it might react with silane coupling agent on glass fibre. As a result, high molecular weight of M-PP established high strength.

Figure 6 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for virgin H1 specimen.

Figure 7 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for virgin H2 specimen.

Figures 4-7 show the bending stress-deflection curves, cumulative AE count and the maximum AE amplitude developed under the bending loading. In L1 specimen AE started to generate at about 100MPa of applied stress in both 140kHz and 1MHz transducers, and rapid development of AE could be observed. In addition, a lot of AE with high amplitude occurred soon after the initiation of AE. H1 specimen showed the same tendency with L1 specimen. In L2 specimen AE also started to generate at about 100MPa of applied stress in 140kHz transducer, however, the amplitude of AE gradually increased with increasing the applied stress. AE detected by 1MHz started to occur later than 140kHz transducer. AE detected by 1MHz transducer was related to the fibre dominant fracture. Therefore AE result indicated that only the matrix cracking occurred prior to the fibre dominant fracture. This tendency was extremely different from L1 specimen. H2 specimen showed the same tendency with L2 specimen. From these results the effect of molecular weight on fracture behaviour was discussed. The molecular weight of matrix PP did not affect the AE characteristics, and only the deformation behaviour was affected by the molecular weight. Lower molecular weight of matrix PP did not show the plastic deformation very much, and as a result, the lower

molecular weight of matrix PP brought the higher strength. The molecular weight of M-PP significantly affected the AE characteristics. In the specimens with lower molecular weight of M-PP the AE count increased rapidly soon after the initiation of AE, and this meant that the developed crack rapidly progressed with increasing the applied stress. This behaviour brought the lower strength. On the other hand, the AE count gradually increased in the specimen with higher molecular weight of M-PP. This meant that the generated crack propagated slowly and it brought the ductile fracture progression under the loading. In addition, the initial fracture mode was only matrix cracking without fibre breakage and its fracture energy should be lower than the fracture following fibre breakage. As a result, the specimens with higher molecular weight of M-PP showed higher bending strength.

Effect of Hydrothermal Aging on Bending Properties

Figure 8 shows the relation between the retention of bending strength and aging time for the wet specimens. The bending strength decreased to 300 hours aging, and it kept

Figure 8 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for H1 specimen.

Figure 9 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for H2 specimen.

almost constant in H1, H2 and L1 specimens. On the other hand, the strength reduction in L2 specimen was quite larger than H1, H2 and L1 specimens. This result suggested that low molecular weight of matrix PP was quite sensitive to hydrothermal aging. Figure 9 shows the relation between the retention of bending strength and aging time for the dry specimens. The bending strengths of dry specimens slightly recovered by removal of absorbed water. The recovery of the strength by drying was remarkable in the specimens with lower molecular weight of M-PP. As mentioned above, the higher molecular weight of M-PP brought the higher initial strength (strength of virgin specimen), however, the bending strength reduction was remarkable.

In order to discuss the mechanism of the strength reduction AE characteristics of the dry specimens were investigated. Figures 10 and 11 show the bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics of L2 and H2 dry specimens after aged for 1000hours. In H2 specimen remarkable change in AE characteristics could not be observed before and after aging. The initiation of AE shifted to lower stress, and only the reduction of damage tolerance occurred in the aged H2 specimen. On the contrary, the AE characteristics of aged L2 specimen drastically changed in comparison of its virgin

Figure 10 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for aged L2 specimen.

Figure 11 Bending stress-deflection curves and AE characteristics for aged H2 specimen.

specimen. The rupture occurred soon after the initiation of AE. Only a few AE count showed in 140kHz transducer, while the great amount of AE generated in 1MHz transducer. This meant that a lot of fibre dominant fracture occurred soon after the development of crack. This change in fracture mechanism brought the significant strength reduction in L2 specimen.

CONCLUSION

In this study the effect of molecular weights of polypropylene on bending properties of GF/PP injection mouldings. 2 types of PP with different molecular weight were adopted as matrix, and 2 types of maleic acid grafted PP were adopted as interphase modifier. The effect of molecular weight was discussed through the bending properties and AE characteristics. In addition, the specimens were aged hydrothermally in order to attack the interphase, and the changes of bending properties were measured. In the virgin specimen bending properties were enhanced by introducing lower molecular weight of matrix PP and higher molecular weight of M-PP, and the bending strength was significantly affected by the molecular weight of M-PP. Higher molecular weight of M-PP brought much ductile nature and it brought the higher strength. However, the bending strength after aging dropped significantly in the specimens with higher molecular weight of M-PP, and remarkable change in fracture mechanism occurred by aging in L2 specimen.

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